

acid, total number of oscillations and total time of oscillation have also been recorded and these were also found to decrease as the concentration of glucose was increased. Again as no reactant was added during the progress of the reaction, the reaction systems were closed in the thermodynamic sense and the general increase in time period with time in gallic acid system is in conformity with expectations. In case of citric acid, although the first oscillation periods at some glucose concentrations are rather abnormal, the periods in general do not change with time as in the case of sustained oscillations.

The effect of glucose on B-Z reaction can be explained in the light of the FKN mechanism, which involves 3 intermediates, the control intermediate, i.e. Br⁻, the switched intermediate, i.e. bromous acid, and the regeneration intermediate, i.e. Fe^{III}, Ce^{IV} ions etc. The following are the probable¹¹ reactions in gallic acid system.

Process A: Reaction of bromide with bromate ion to yield bromine. This last species undergoes fast reaction with gallic acid to generate bromogallic acid (BrHG).

Process B: Autocatalytic formation of bromous acid with a rapid oxidation of Fe²⁺ to Fe³⁺.

This process is important only when Br⁻ is under a critical value, bromide ion being an inhibitor of process B by step A2. There is an autocatalytic production of HBrO₂ limited by its dismutation in step B2. In the process B, there is a very rapid accumulation of Fe³⁺.

Process C: A recovery process.

This process is the Fe³⁺ oxidation of organic brominated species and generates a bromide ion, thus switching back the reaction to the process A.

As the process A proceeds, the process C continues to deplete Fe³⁺ from the reaction mixture, enabling the bromide concentration to undergo the critical value below which the process B can be switched again.

The reducing property of glucose is perhaps responsible for the decrease of induction period as well as oscillation period. It competes with gallic acid for bromine¹² (or other bromine species in higher oxidation states) as a result of which Br₂ is

quickly consumed and process A takes place quickly. It also controls the formation of Br⁻ because bromogallic acid, which is the chief regenerator of Br⁻ through process C is formed in smaller amount in its presence. As a result, process B (which is significant at low Br⁻ concentration) starts sooner. The net result is that the induction period is decreased, oscillation starts sooner and the oscillations are quickly completed decreasing the oscillation period. The total number of oscillations as also the total time of oscillation decrease as bromate is consumed more in each cycle in presence of glucose. As the concentration of glucose is increased, all of these values decrease. It is likely that in citric acid system a similar mechanism is operative.

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Synthesis and Fungicidal Activity of Some Mixed 5-Pyrazolone and 5-Thiopyrazolone Derivatives

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IT has been observed from our earlier work on heterocyclic fungicides¹⁻⁵ that 5-pyrazonones possess significant fungicidal activity against the rice blast pathogen *Pyricularia oryzae* and the brown leaf spot pathogen *Helminthosporium oryzae*. The survey of literature further reveals that thiopyrazo-

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NOTES

lones also exhibit encouraging antifungal activity^{6,7}. In view of the marked biological importance associated with these two classes of compounds the present investigation has extended to synthesise some new derivatives containing both the two active nuclei.

Two methods have been adopted for synthesis of 1-aryl-1-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one)-1-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5-thione) methane. The first method was the Michael addition of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-monoarylidene-5-one with 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione. The second method was the Michael addition of the 4-monoarylidene-2-pyrazolin-5-thione with 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one. The identity of the compounds prepared by these two different methods were established from their undepressed m.p. and superimposition of ir spectra. The structure of these compounds were established from their elemental analysis, ir and mass spectral studies. The ir spectra of compound I showed bands at ~ 3030 (enolic), 1610 (C=O) and 1130 cm⁻¹ (C=S). Further, the mass spectra of this compound record molecular ion (m/e) value 452. The values of 263 and 190 are due to the two parent moieties formed by the rupture of CH-CH linkage. Due to the removal of R-CH an absorption appears at 173. Further, the values of 91, 77, 52, 32 and 28 are attributable to Ph-N⁺, Ph, C₄H₄⁺, S⁺ and CO⁺, respectively which are obtained by similar fragmentation of both the pyrazolone moiety.

The cyclopropane derivatives of these compounds were prepared by dissolving the parent compound I in 20% NaOH solution and subsequent treatment with a saturated solution of iodine-potassium iodide. The structure of these cyclopropane derivatives were confirmed from their elemental analysis and spectral studies. The spectra of II(1) showed bands at 1710 (C=O), 1140 (C=S) and 3200-3110 cm⁻¹ (CH in cyclopropane ring), and m/e value of 450 in agreement with its molecular weight.

All the compounds thus prepared were screened for their fungicidal activity against the rice blast pathogen *P. oryzae* and brown leaf spot pathogen *H. oryzae* using the spore germination tests at various concentrations by the standard method. The fungicidal activity of the mixed derivatives at 1000 ppm concentration are recorded in Table 1 and those of their cyclopropane derivatives in Table 2. In general, the rate of germination inhibition was found to be higher in case of the compounds contained in Table 1 than their cyclopropane derivatives. The compounds no. 2, 4, 5, 12 and 15 (Table 1) showed encouraging fungitoxicity against both the pathogens. Further, compounds no. 1, 2, 5, 10 and 17 were active against *P. oryzae*, and 1, 9 and 11 against *H. oryzae*. The compound no. 2 of this series showed highest antifungal activity inhibiting 89 and 85% spore germination of *P. oryzae* and *H. oryzae*, respectively at 1000 ppm concentration.

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL AND FUNGICIDAL DATA OF 1-ARYL-1-(1-PHENYL-3-METHYL-2-PYRAZOLIN-5-ONE)-1-(1-PHENYL-3'-METHYL-2'-PYRAZOLIN-5'-THIONE)-METHANE (I)

R = C₆H₅ (1-19), R₁ = C₆H₅ (1-10), H (11-19)

Compd. no.	R ₂	M. p. °C	Sulphur % ; Found (Calcd.)	Yield %	Germination inhibition % at 1000 ppm <i>P. oryzae</i> / <i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	C ₆ H ₅	132	7.20 (7.07)	50	61/58
2.	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	55	6.15 (6.83)	48	89/85
3.	<i>m</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	73	6.20 (6.83)	45	52/48
4.	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	70	6.45 (6.83)	45	57/70
5.	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	95	6.05 (6.43)	55	80/61
6.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	185	6.65 (6.43)	50	48/41
7.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	140	6.89 (6.43)	55	44/53
8.	OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	75	5.94 (6.63)	45	39/53
9.	OHOCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	310	5.85 (6.42)	48	45/57
10.	C ₄ H ₉ O	100	7.02 (7.23)	45	68/28
11.	C ₆ H ₅	120	9.85 (8.51)	50	45/57
12.	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	140	9.92 (8.16)	55	58/87
13.	<i>m</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	240	9.82 (8.16)	50	47/37
14.	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	210	9.45 (8.16)	45	51/53
15.	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	170	8.98 (7.60)	50	73/60
16.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	280	8.68 (7.60)	45	35.51
17.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	137	8.86 (7.60)	48	79/37
18.	OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	84	8.05 (7.88)	45	45/54
19.	OHOCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	73	8.10 (7.58)	40	37/53

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL AND FUNGICIDAL DATA OF CYCLOPROPANE DERIVATIVES OF 1-ARYL-1-(1-PHENYL-3-METHYL-2-PYRAZOLIN-5-ONE)-1-(1'-PHENYL-3'-METHYL-2'-PYRAZOLIN-5'-THIONE)-METHANE (II)

R = C₆H₅ (1–19), R₁ = C₆H₅ (1–10), H (11–19)

Compd. no.	R ₂	M. p. °C	Sulphur % ; Found/ (Calcd.)	Yield %	Germination inhibition % at 1000 ppm <i>P. oryzae</i> / <i>H. oryzae</i>
1.	C ₆ H ₅	90	8.10 (7.11)	40	54/37
2.	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	150	6.32 (6.86)	45	40/33
3.	<i>m</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	160	6.05 (6.86)	40	70/57
4.	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	125	6.15 (6.86)	35	39/45
5.	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	192	6.23 (6.46)	45	67/63
6.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	90	6.96 (6.46)	40	43/40
7.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	170	6.20 (6.46)	42	47/35
8.	OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	121	6.95 (6.66)	50	41/44
9.	OH-3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	110	7.03 (6.45)	45	40/42
10.	C ₄ H ₉ O	75	7.00 (7.27)	40	61/60
11.	C ₆ H ₅	105	8.25 (8.55)	45	37/32
12.	<i>o</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	177	9.98 (8.20)	40	57/52
13.	<i>m</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	120	9.87 (8.20)	38	42/43
14.	<i>p</i> -OHC ₆ H ₄	190	9.63 (8.20)	35	47/39
15.	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	155	8.09 (7.63)	45	40/38
16.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	300	8.17 (7.63)	42	53/41
17.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	240	8.23 (7.63)	40	51/53
18.	OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	125	8.21 (7.92)	35	38/40
19.	C ₄ H ₉ O	73	8.09 (8.42)	42	28/43

Out of 19 cyclopropane derivatives (Table 2), compounds no. 3, 5 and 10 showed considerable activity against both the pathogens. Encouraging results were not noticed with the rest of the compounds. So it is concluded that the formation of cyclopropane ring in these compounds retards the activity markedly.

The relevant data on elemental analysis, m.p. and fungitoxicity results are presented in Table 1 and 2.

Experimental

1-Aryl-1-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-one)-1-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5'-thione) methane (I): Method A: 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-monoarylidene-5-pyrazolone (0.01 mol) was taken in ethanol (20 ml) and to it an alkaline solution of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (0.01 mol) was added drop-

wise. The mixture was refluxed for 4 h over water bath. Then excess alcohol was evaporated off and the resulting mixture acidified with cold dil. HCl. A light pink coloured compound precipitated out was filtered, washed with distilled water and finally dried in vacuum. Crystallisation of the solid from ethanol yielded light pink crystals (70%), m.p. 132°. The compound was soluble in 10% NaOH solution and gave colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃.

Method B: A mixture of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-mono-arylidene-2-pyrazolin-5-thione (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) and 1-phenyl-3-methyl-5-pyrazolone (0.01 mol) in 10% NaOH solution (25 ml) was refluxed for 4 h over water bath. The excess of ethanol was evaporated and the mass was acidified with cold dil. HCl. A light pink coloured solid precipitated out was filtered, washed with distilled water, dried in vacuum and finally crystallised from ethanol to yield light pink crystals (75%), m.p. 132°. The compound was soluble in 10% NaOH solution and gave red colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃.

Cyclopropane derivatives of 1-aryl-1-(1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one)-1-(1'-phenyl-3'-methyl-2'-pyrazolin-5'-thione) methane (II): Compound I (5 g) was dissolved in 20% NaOH solution (25 ml) and to it a saturated solution of iodine in potassium iodide (20 ml) was added dropwise with constant stirring for 2 h. The brown precipitate thus obtained was filtered and washed with 20% sodium thiosulphate solution and then with distilled water and finally crystallised from ethanol to yield light brown crystals (50%), m.p. 90°. The compound was insoluble in 10% NaOH solution and gave no colouration with alcoholic FeCl₃ solution.

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